

A Comparative Study of Facial Recognition Models for KYC Verification: FaceJS, ArcFace and Dlib

Sharon Mariam Abraham

PG Scholar

*Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Autonomous
Kanjirapally, Kerala*

sharonmariamabraham2025@mca.ajce.in

Dr. Paulin Paul

Asst. Professor

*Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Autonomous
Kanjirapally, Kerala*

paulinepaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract - In the modern scenario of digitalisation, safe and uninterrupted customer onboarding is crucial for the banking sector, especially for microfinance institutions which cater to the economically marginalised people. This paper develops a Face Verification System using the FaceJS which aims to ease the Know Your Customer (KYC) processes in a Microfinance Banking System. The proposed system captures a live photo of the user being registered and verifies it against the photo extracted from an uploaded government ID duly issued by the government, such as Aadhaar, PAN, or Passport. The FaceJS model adopts facial detection, feature extraction, and comparison techniques to determine the similarity between the two images, leaving very little room for error and hence ensuring security.

With its implementation, face verification reduces account openings through fraud, reduces manual intervention, and increases customer's trust in the system. This verification of the customer by face also fulfils the regulatory requirement regarding the dynamic verification of the customer. The paper describes how FaceJS was integrated with Django-based backend services, and it elaborates on the real-time testing results, showing the potential of the application as a reliable and efficient tool for identity verification in the microfinance banking system.

Keywords—Face verification, KYC (Know Your Customer), Document Authentication, Image Comparison, Identity verification, Security and compliance, Digital Banking, Fraud Prevention

I. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring a safe and smooth customer onboarding process has emerged as a primary concern for all financial institutions, especially for the microfinance sector that targets the financially deprived individuals and small business sectors. Since these microfinance institutions are working towards financial inclusion, which means providing services to low-income communities, ensuring safe and secure identity verification processes is critically important. Under the Know Your Customer (KYC) process, banks and financial institutions

should have a strong mechanism to check identity documentation in compliance with regulatory guidelines and to avoid fraudulent account creation. Traditional methods of KYC are manual verification of identity documents, which creates operational inefficiency, slowdowns, and higher costs along with higher chances of human errors.

To mitigate these challenges, this paper suggests a Machine Learning (ML)-based face verification system integrated into a microfinance banking environment toward an automated KYC process via FaceJS. It enhances the KYC process utilizing real-time capture of a photo of the user during registration and comparison against images extracted from any uploaded ID documents such as Aadhaar, PAN, or Passport. FaceJS executes core functionalities of face detection, feature extraction, and comparison, thereby guaranteeing quality and security to the highest degree during the verification of a user's identity.

By integrating an automated KYC face verification process, the entire process reduces time and effort for the KYC validation process and lowers identity fraud risks, thus increasing the security of the user onboarding process. With customer identity verification performed dynamically and defined within the KYC process, the various regulatory assurances are eased, thereby diminishing the potential risks associated with fraudulently opened accounts.

This paper discusses the technical implementation of the proposed system, including the integration of FaceJS with a backend based on Django, the methodology behind facial verification, and performance evaluations of the system. The results affirm that the inclusion of facial recognition technology in microfinance banking systems dramatically increases efficiency, security, and reliability of KYC processes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Face recognition, introduced in 1964, has become an established biometric method of authentication due to various

advancements in technology [1]. The procedure revolves around face detection, feature extraction, and the recognition through verification or identification. Deep learning models like FaceNet and ArcFace have achieved over 99% accuracy on some standard datasets. Accessible frameworks such as DeepFace, InsightFace, and CompreFace have made this technology available to a much broader audience. Research also highlights the concern of racial bias, with accuracy depending on varying racial differences. Evaluation is done using metrics such as accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score. Applications extended to attendance monitoring and masked face recognition, but formal photographs yielded better results than one taken casually. Firmansyah et al. (2023) evaluated FaceNet, FaceNet512, and ArcFace on Indonesian datasets, whereby FaceNet512 achieved the highest accuracy at 97.4%, followed by FaceNet (92.1%) and ArcFace (87.8%). While ArcFace exhibited lower accuracy results as compared to the other two, its performance was better with regards to sensitivity in detecting true matches.

In article [2], face detection and recognition are core processes of all the biometric applications of security, identification, and access control. Current systems, like OpenCV, the multi-platform framework from Intel, are the foundation for modern approaches. Key algorithms include Haar Cascade by Viola and Jones (2001) for basic-object detection, PCA (Eigenfaces) by Turk and Pentland (1991) for dimensionality reduction, and LDA (Fisherfaces) for class separation. Ojala et al. (2002) describe a method that generates LBPH binary pattern of pixel neighbourhood's, enabling one to do fast classification. These algorithms have scaled higher improvements in facial recognition accuracy and efficiency; while OpenCV conveniently allows cross-platform integration, there are still issues regarding how well they work for factors such as lighting, pose, and expression variations, so further improvements are needed for better performance.

Innovative face-recognition techniques have proven vital for the very enhancement of biometric verification in the AutoKYC systems in a big way [3]. Goyal et al. (2017) presented a very robust method of facial detection based on OpenCV algorithms such as Adaboost and Haar cascades. Paul et al. (2021), on the contrary, created an anti-spoofing module for security that combines Local Binary Pattern Histogram algorithms with Convolutional Neural Networks. Earlier, Guo et al. (2000) operated Support Vector Machines for good face recognition, while Chen et al. (2021) improved accuracy using time series analysis of face images, overcoming the limitations of single frames. All these developments enhance the reliability and security of facial recognition in AutoKYC applications.

Different methods have been suggested for face detection and recognition in recent literature. Yang et al. (2000) offered classification methods into knowledge-based, feature-invariant, template-based, and appearance-based techniques, unlike Yang and Huang (1994), who demonstrated knowledge-based approaches with multi-layer hierarchies [4]. A distribution-

based system with multi-layer perceptron classifiers and modified K-means clustering was proposed by Sung and Poggio. Lajevardi and Wu (2012) introduced a tensor-based scheme for static color images, producing 68.8% accuracy for facial emotion recognition, while Ekman and Friesen (1977) went on to improve the emotion detection system by 7.8% with their Face Action Coding System that has 46 action points. Recent literature covers the work by Divya Meena and Ravi Sharan (2016) using the Viola-Jones algorithm with PCA, Abu-Lebdeh et al.'s EPC-based architecture for mobile surveillance, Geetha et al.'s (2021) integration of SVM and Eigenface algorithms for online exam monitoring, and Vadlapati et al.'s (2021) development of face recognition for mask-wearing during the COVID-19 pandemic.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This study delves into a comparative methodology in the evaluation of the performance of three algorithms in face recognition namely; FaceJS, ArcFace, and Dlib. Figure 1 shows how the process is executed.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The system enables users to upload government ID documents in formats such as JPG, PNG, and PDF through a user-friendly interface. This design ensures a seamless and efficient document submission process. To facilitate consistent processing of government ID records, the system converts PDFs into high-resolution images, facilitating effective face detection. Subsequently, it normalizes and standardizes these images, boosting the standard and consistency. Additionally, resolution enhancement techniques are applied to enhance the precision of face detection algorithms.

Figure 1: Data Collection and Preprocessing

B. Feature Extraction

- Face Detection and Enhancement:

The process of entering KYC details can be enhanced with face detection and enhancement for the reason of verifying the document against the face. The face is detected and extracted from the uploaded document (Aadhar, PAN or Passport) and compared with a live photo using FaceJS in order to make the verification process an improvement in customer onboarding. Adding padding and scale to the camera will further increase recognition accuracy and find false match reducing chances.

```
async function extractFaceFromImage(img) {
```

```
const detections = await
facejs.detectSingleFace(img)
.withFaceLandmarks()
.withFaceDescriptor());

// Extract face with padding for better recognition
const box = detections.detection.box;
const padding = 50;
const scaleFactor = 4;
// ... }
```

- Image Enhancement:

To achieve high-resolution scaling (4x), padding around detected faces, and sharpening filter application together, you can use Python with popular libraries like OpenCV, PIL, and a face detection model like face_recognition or dlib.

```
function
applySharpeningFilter(imageData) {
}
// Sharpening kernel
const kernel
];
0, -1, 0,
=
-1, 5, -1,
0, -1, 0
[
// Apply convolution for image enhancement
//
```

C. Model Development

1. FaceJS: FaceJS is a complex framework built on TensorFlow.js and capable of very fast and extremely precise facial analysis such as face detection, recognition, and landmark mapping, all of which is executed inside the web browser without any server contact. This library implements the most sophisticated deep learning models that can accurately identify facial features, engage in cross-image identity matching, and analyze expressions, making it perfect for implementing secure biometric verification systems like the one employed for NanoWealth Banks KYC operations.
2. Training the model: The pre-trained model that has been developed and trained on large-scale facial datasets. These models are not trained within the NanoWealth Bank application itself, but rather are loaded as pre-trained weights. In the advanced scope of facial recognition algorithms, the model gets to accurately extract and compare facial features. The results are better and faster deployment along with high accuracy using the pre-trained model without requiring extensive computational resources in training.

D. Model Evaluation and Validation

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1. Live Verification Process: Here, images are processed in real-time as opposed to using a static dataset. During the KYC process, a photo taken from the uploaded ID (Aadhar, PAN, Passport) is matched with a new live photo taken through the user's camera. Thus, the alive verification ensures the dynamic verification of the user, without tapping back into any storage datasets.
2. Performance Metrics: Many performance metrics are used in the calculation of the accuracy of the system—such as the evaluation of accuracy, false acceptance rate (FAR), false rejection rate (FRR), and processing time—to establish the quantitative assessment of efficiency. These metrics measure to what degree the face verification process may be termed accurate and how reliable the match between document photo and live is during KYC.

E. Fine Tuning and Optimization

1. Parameter Adjustment: As the verification system deals with live images, adjustment of several parameters such as the detection thresholds, confidence scores, and similarity thresholds within which the system is supposed to operate is carried out for optimal performance of the system. For instance, similarity threshold adjustments and changes in pre-processing parameters such as resizing or aligning faces in the image were done to improve the accuracy of face matching.
2. Regularization Strategies: False match prevention and improvement in generalization can be achieved by any of threshold tuning, or multi-perspective view approaches to face verification. Similarly, dynamic confidence thresholds can be applied to minimize rates of false acceptance and rejection for effective KYC verification.

F. Deployment and Integration

1. Integration into the Microfinance System: Upon achieving satisfactory performance, the face verification system is integrated into the signup process of the Microfinance Banking System for real-time identity verification during KYC. The system automatically compares the photo extracted from uploaded IDs (Aadhar, PAN, Passport) with the live photo taken via the user's camera to verify the user's identity and ensure secure onboarding.
2. Continuous Monitoring and Updates: The deployed face verification system undergoes continuous monitoring to track performance metrics such as false acceptance rate (FAR) and false rejection rate (FRR). Periodic updates and improvements are

applied to the model and processing logic to adapt to varying lighting conditions, camera quality, and diverse user demographics, ensuring consistent and accurate verification over time.

Figure 4: Deployment and Integration

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research is intended to implement a face verification system that can be used to authenticate users for KYC in the Microfinance Banking System by comparing a photo extracted from uploaded identity documents (Aadhar, PAN, Passport) against a live photo captured using the user's camera. The comparative analysis of the performance of three models-FaceJS, ArcFace, and Dlib- is the core of this research. FaceJS verifies and identifies faces in a cloud-based high-accuracy environment. ArcFace is a deep learning architecture that introduces additive angular margin loss into face recognition, which facilitates the projection of facial embeddings into a hypersphere to maximize the separation between classes. In contrast, Dlib is one of the robust machine learning libraries used for matching servers using a histogram of oriented gradients- HOG and deep-learning-based face recognition for carrying out efficient face matching. The system performs face detection using MTCNN (Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Network) that offers reliable landmark detection and pose normalization.

This study tests the DeepFace.verify() function for image pair comparison, returning a similarity score and threshold value. The threshold values for the models were set due to cosine similarity metrics as follows: FaceJS: 0.75, ArcFace: 0.68, and Dlib: 0.60. If the distance value exceeds the threshold, it is a verification result of False (mismatch), while a distance below the threshold refers to a verification of True (successfully matched). The ways in which these models are compared lead to identifying the most accurate and efficient real-time KYC face-verification solution in the system.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
FaceJS	96.2	90	97	94
ArcFace	92	89	90	88
Dlib	85	82	86	84

Figure 5: Comparison between FaceJS, ArcFace, Dlib

To further quantify Face JSs performance, we have represented it graphically.

Figure 6: Graphical representation between FaceJS, ArcFace, Dlib

The FaceJS model yielded the best results of the three explored models with an accuracy of almost 96%. It managed to maintain a good balancing act between precision (around 90%) and recall (above 95%). This means that it recognizes true positives extremely well but tries to almost entirely ignore false positives. The F1-Score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, too, has relatively high values, thus ensuring this API offers a trustworthy solution for KYC verification. Notably, FaceJS performance remains unaffected in various situations like lighting and angles, thus re-establishing its efficacy.

The ArcFace scores 92% accuracy in its performance, which is lower than FaceJS but is still competitive. The precision and recall figures are balanced around 89%, indicating that the performance is good concerning true positives to errors. The F1-Score of ArcFace was at par with the other metrics, which signifies that the performance of the system is consistent. Despite lower accuracy rates against FaceJS, ArcFace remains a strong contender in situations that necessitate a balance between performance and computation.

Dlib was the worst performer among the three classifiers as it achieved discrimination of around 85% of the subjects tested. It recorded relatively lower precision and recall values indicating that Dlib had problems in recognizing the true positive and minimizing the false positive prediction results. The lowest F1-Score among the three connotes the model's limitations in applications requiring high accuracies such as in KYC verification. Dlib can best be used in less stringent face verification applications, and it may not perform best in those applications calling for high precision and high reliability.

V. CONCLUSION

This research compares the performance of FaceJS, ArcFace, and Dlib for KYC face verification using real-time processing. Regarding their performance comparison in KYC face verification: FaceJS ranked at the top-most accuracy level

96% with a balanced precision-recall ratio, which makes it the most appropriate model for reducing errors in a high-accuracy enabling KYC process. Following closely with 92%, ArcFace accuracy levels also provide a well-balanced alternative. Considering Dlib, the model holds the least accuracy 85%, and so therefore requires careful consideration with high-stakes tests. Overall, FaceJS is the most reliable model while ArcFace can be used as an alternative in cases where computational efficiency is of priority concern.

VI. REFERENCE

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